

Cross condensation reactions of ethyl cyanoacetate with some ketomethylene compounds : Diastereoselective synthesis of *Z*-2-(cyanoethoxycarbonyl)methylene-1,2-dihydropyridine and *Z*-2-(cyanoethoxycarbonyl)methylene-2*H*-pyran derivatives†

Sunil K. Talapatra*, Kabita Mandal, Kallolmay Biswas, Sudipta Mandal and Bani Talapatra*

Centre of Advanced Studies on Natural Products, Department of Chemistry, University College of Science, University of Calcutta, Calcutta-700 009, India

Manuscript received 14 October 1999

Previously reported ethyl α,ϵ -dicyano- β,δ -dimethyl- $\Delta^{\beta,\delta}$ -hexadienoate (2) structure for the minor product of the diethylamine catalyzed condensation reaction between ethyl cyanoacetate and acetylacetone has now been revised as 4,6-dimethyl-*Z*-2-(cyanoethoxycarbonyl)methylene-1,2-dihydropyridine (3) based on its ^1H NMR, ^{13}C NMR and mass spectral analyses. The formation of the major product 3-carboethoxy-4,6-dimethyl-2*H*-pyridone (1), and of 3 from 1 has been rationalized. The exocyclic substituted methylene moiety has been shown to have *Z* configuration, based on diastereomeric transition states as predicted mechanistically. However, 3 has been isolated as the sole product of the above condensation when mediated by K_2CO_3 . Similarly, K_2CO_3 mediated condensation of ethyl cyanoacetate with ethyl acetoacetate gives 3-cyano-4-hydroxy-6-methyl-*Z*-2-(cyanoethoxycarbonyl)methylene-2*H*-pyran (4) and that with 2-hydroxy-4,6-dimethylacetophenone affords 3-cyano-4,5,7-trimethylcoumarin (5) and 4,5,7-trimethyl-*Z*-2-(cyanoethoxycarbonyl)methylenebenzo[*b*]-2*H*-pyran (6). Diastereoselective formation of the *Z* isomers 4 and 6 has been accounted for in terms of the diastereomeric transition states of the reactions.

Ethyl cyanoacetate is known to undergo condensation with ketones and aldehydes in presence of a secondary amine, sodium ethoxide or weak bases.

Cross condensation of ethyl cyanoacetate and acetylacetone :

It was reported¹ that ethyl cyanoacetate, when treated with acetylacetone in molar proportion in presence of diethylamine yielded 3-carboethoxy-4,6-dimethyl-2*H*-pyridone (1), m.p. 135°, as the major product, along with a minor product, m.p. 190°, for which structure 2 (ethyl α,ϵ -dicyano- β,δ -dimethyl- $\Delta^{\beta,\delta}$ -hexadienoate) was suggested.

As part of an ongoing research programme in the area of our synthetic studies² on some heterocycles using substrates endowed with both nucleophilic and electrophilic sites, we performed the above cross condensation reaction under the condition described earlier¹ and also by using a weak base like K_2CO_3 . We obtained, in the first case both the compounds having m.ps. 135° and 190° and in the second case only the 190° compound having molecular weight 218, in agreement with that for structure 2. The ^1H and ^{13}C NMR

and mass spectral analyses allowed us to confirm structure 1 for the 135° compound but to revise unambiguously the structure 2 of 190° compound as 3.

A probable mechanism of the formation of 1 is shown in Scheme 1, where one molecule of ethyl cyanoacetate carbanion reacts with one molecule of acetylacetone in the expected manner to form ethyl α -cyano- δ -keto- β -methyl- Δ^{β} -hexenoate (A) as an intermediate which then undergoes molecular rearrangement and forms 1.

Structural analogy between 1 and 3 suggests that 3 might have been formed through the intermediacy of 1 which demands decarboethoxylation at some stage. This conjecture

Scheme 1. Probable pathway of the formation of 1.

†Dedicated with profound respect to Professor D. Nasipuri on the occasion of his 75th. birth anniversary.

received support experimentally. Thus **1** when refluxed with 1.2 molar proportion of ethyl cyanoacetate formed **3**.

Compound **3** showed the presence of two aromatic methyls (δ 2.41 and 2.29, each 3H singlet), two meta-coupled protons (δ 6.77 and 6.19, 1H, bs each), one NH (δ 13.56 bs, 1H) and an ethyl group (δ 4.16, 2H, q and 1.27, 3H, t, $J \approx 7$ Hz) as a part of a carboethoxy group. The presence of these structural components were further supported by its ^{13}C NMR spectral data. Additionally, all the non-protonated carbon atoms could also be identified. The ^{13}C NMR spectra (PND and APT) showed the presence of two aromatic methyl carbons (δ 21.69 and 19.54), two heteroaromatic monoprotonated carbons (δ 116.11 and 114.21), a carboethoxy group (δ 170.69, 59.83 and 14.4), a cyano group (δ 119.78) and three more quaternary carbons [δ 155.39 (C-6), 143.9 (C-4) and 61.1 (=C(CN)-CO₂Et)]. The chemical shift δ 61.6 is attributed to the cyano containing quaternary carbon in view of the chemical shifts of such quaternary carbons in some compounds^{3,4}.

The electrophilicity of the lactam carbonyl is increased by the carboethoxy group at C-3, the presence of which significantly contributes to the canonical form **1a** and consequently the atomic coefficient of LUMO of the lactam carbonyl is probably greater than the atomic coefficient of the LUMO of the carboethoxy carbonyl. Thus the former becomes the preferred site of attack by the HOMO of the ethyl cyanoacetate carbanion. The probable path for the forma-

tion of **3** from **1** is delineated in Scheme 2. Mechanistically decarboethoxylation takes place after the generation of the double bond at C-2.

The *Z* stereochemistry of the tetrasubstituted double bond, as predicted from its probable mechanism, received support from the spectral data.

The nucleophilic attack of the chiral methine carbanion (*R* enantiomer shown) of another molecule of ethyl cyanoacetate on the *Si* (α -)face of the amide carbonyl of **1** in a staggered manner minimizes the torsional strain^{5,6} in the transition state **TS-B** and facilitates the formation of H-bonding between the amide NH and the ester CO groups and thus lowers the **TS-B** energy and leads to the intermediate *parf* (*Si-Si*)^{7,8} diastereomer (**B**) (Scheme 2). The facile E2 elimination of the elements of H₂O from the preferred conformer (**a**) having H and OH in antiperiplanar orientation and arising directly from **TS-B**, gives rise to **3** with *Z* configuration around the exocyclic double bond as the sole product. The intramolecularly H-bonded ester CO (with NH) appeared at the lower IR frequency at 1610–1640 cm⁻¹ thus supporting the *Z* configuration. The other two possible conformers (**b**) and (**c**) having H and OH in gauche orientation cannot undergo E2 elimination.

The alternative pathway (Scheme 3) involves the attack of the *S* enantiomer of the chiral methine carbanion of ethyl cyanoacetate on the *Si* (α -)face of the amide carbonyl of **1** in a staggered manner; no H-bonding stabilization between NH and CO is possible in the resulting diastereomeric transition state **TS-C** which additionally involves strong gauche interaction between the bulky CO₂Et groups and is, therefore, of comparatively higher energy. Hence this pathway

Scheme 2. Probable pathway of the formation of **3** (*Z* isomer).

Scheme 3. Alternative disfavoured pathway.

leading to the intermediate *pref*(*Si-Re*)^{7,8} diastereomer (C) is disfavoured. Again, its conformer (d) having H and OH groups in the antiperiplanar orientation, which upon E2 elimination would give rise to 3' (the *E* isomer of 3), involves high activation energy for H₂O elimination due to strong eclipsing interaction between the bulky CO₂Et groups in the transition state so much so that the olefin 3', the corresponding *E* isomer of 3, was not apparently formed.

The K₂CO₃-mediated condensation of ethyl cyanoacetate has been extended to other ketomethylene compounds.

Cross condensation between ethyl cyanoacetate and other ketomethylene compounds :

Ethyl cyanoacetate underwent K₂CO₃-mediated condensation with ethyl acetoacetate to give an oxygen heterocycle, 3-cyano-4-hydroxy-6-methyl-*Z*-2-(cyanoethoxycarbonyl)methylene-2*H*-pyran (4) in good yield (~70%) as a single product. The probable favoured pathway leading to the formation of 4 is shown in Scheme 4. One molecule of each compound condenses to form an α -pyrone derivative which

Scheme 4. Probable favoured pathway of the formation of 4 (*Z* isomer).

undergoes condensation with the *R*-carbanion of another molecule of ethyl cyanoacetate to form the *pref* diastereomer (D) through the TS-D. The preferred chelated conformer (g) then undergoes dehydration by E2 mechanism through the TS (vide g) stabilized by chelation and having no eclipsing interaction. The two other conformers (h) and (i) (not shown) having H and OH in gauche orientation cannot undergo E2 elimination. The alternative disfavoured

pathway (Scheme 5) involves high energy TS-E leading to the *parf* diastereomer (E), the (j) conformer of which again involves strong eclipsing interaction between CO₂Et and CN groups and no stabilization through chelation in the TS (vide conformer j) leading to the *E* isomer 4' which was not apparently formed (Scheme 5).

Scheme 5. Alternative disfavoured pathway.

Cross condensation of ethyl cyanoacetate with 2,4-dimethyl-6-hydroxyacetophenone under the same condition yielded first 3-cyano-4,5,7-trimethylcoumarin (5) in low yield (~25%). The latter undergoes condensation with another molecule of ethyl cyanoacetate (*R*-carbanion) to form the *pref* diastereomer (F), the preferred chelated conformer (m) of which undergoes E2 elimination to form 4,5,7-trimethyl-*Z*-2-(cyanoethoxycarbonyl)methylenebenzo[*b*]-2*H*-pyran (6) in about 30% yield (Scheme 6). Here also the *E* isomer (6') could not be isolated. Its formation is presumably disfavoured due to the involvement of the higher energy TS-G leading to the *parf* diastereomer (G), the *p* conformer of which does not have any stabilization due to chelation and involves high TS energy due to eclipsing interaction leading to the *E* isomer 6' (Scheme 7).

The structures of compounds 4-6 were established unambiguously from their spectral data (vide Experimental). Some *Z*-2-cyanomethylene derivatives of functionalized pyran-2-ones have recently been reported⁹, of course, following a different reaction sequence. In those cases also no *E* isomer was reported. The *Z* stereochemistry of compounds 4 and 6, assigned on the basis of mechanistic rationale, may be unambiguously established by X-ray crystallographic studies.

Scheme 6. Probable pathway of the formation of 5 and 6.

Scheme 7. Alternative disfavoured pathway

Experimental

M.ps. measured in open capillary are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were measured on a Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer. ^1H NMR (at 300 MHz) and ^{13}C NMR (at 75.5 MHz) were recorded in CDCl_3 on a Bruker-300A spectrophotometer; the peak for solvent (CHCl_3 : δ 7.26 or CDCl_3 : δ 77.0); TMS used as internal standard; J values expressed in Hz. Mass spectra were recorded in an MS-50 instrument at 70 eV. Light petrol used had b.p. 60–80°. Silica gel (60–120 mesh, Qualigen) was used for column chromatography and silica gel G for tlc.

General procedure: The compounds under investigation were refluxed in pairs for 7–12 h in presence of K_2CO_3 (0.005 mol). The alcohol produced during condensation reaction was removed by distillation in each case. The gummy

residue thus obtained was chromatographed over silica gel, elution being carried out with solvents and solvent mixtures of increasing polarity. Fractions were collected in 100 ml portions and monitored by tlc on microslides. The fractions showing similar spots were combined and rechromatographed. Purification of the products required repeated chromatography followed by crystallization from suitable solvent or solvent mixtures.

Cross condensation of acetylacetone and ethyl cyanoacetate in presence of triethylamine: A mixture of acetyl acetone (5 g, 5 ml) and ethyl cyanoacetate (4.5 g, 4.3 ml) in molar proportion was refluxed on a water-bath for 12 h in presence of triethylamine (2 ml). After removal of the triethylamine and unreacted substrates under reduced pressure, the residue obtained was subjected to column chromatography.

3-Carboethoxy-4,6-dimethyl-2H-pyridone (1): The light yellow solid obtained from the light petrol-ethyl acetate (93 : 7) eluate fractions (10–25) of the main chromatogram showing a single spot ($R_f = 0.5$; silica gel, CHCl_3) on tlc afforded 3-carboethoxy-4,6-dimethyl-2H-pyridone (1), crystallizing from chloroform-light petrol as light yellow needles (0.2 g, 30%), m.p. 135°, (lit. 135°); ν_{max} 2990 (aromatic C-H), 1722 (ester CO), 1650 (lactam CO), 1635, 1620, 1550, 1485, 1430 (aromatic C=C), 1390, 1262, 1225, 1180, 1090, 1020, 955, 840, 815, 790, 635, 610 cm^{-1} ; δ_{H} 2.25 (3H, s, CH_3), 2.16 (3H, s, CH_3), 5.89 (1H, bs, H-5), 13.39 (1H, bs, NH), 4.33 (2H, q, $\text{COOCH}_2\text{CH}_3$), 1.30 (3H, t, $\text{COOCH}_2\text{CH}_3$); δ_{C} 19.63 (CH_3), 18.48 (CH_3), 108.5 (C-5), 162.5 ($\text{COOCH}_2\text{CH}_3$), 60.61 ($\text{COOCH}_2\text{CH}_3$), 13.93 ($\text{COOCH}_2\text{CH}_3$), 166.33 (NHCO), 119.91 (C-3), 151.79 (C-4), 146.48 (C-6).

4,6-Dimethyl-Z-2-(cyanoethoxycarbonyl)-1,2-dihydropyridine (3): The later light petrol-ethyl acetate (9 : 1) eluate fractions (26–30) gave a light yellow crystalline solid, identified as 4,6-dimethyl-Z-2-(cyanoethoxycarbonyl)-1,2-dihydropyridine (3; 0.45 g, 9%), m.p. 190°, showing its homogeneity on tlc plate: ν_{max} 2990 (chelated NH), 2910 (aromatic C-H), 2190 (CN), 1610–1640 br [ester CO (chelated)], 1505, 1475, 1370, 1300, 1230, 1175, 1155, 1085, 1030, 980, 890, 850, 765 cm^{-1} ; m/z (% rel. int.) 218 (M^+ , 100), 190 (17), 171 (48), 172 ($\text{M}^+ - \text{EtOH}$, 90), 146 ($\text{M}^+ - \text{CO}_2\text{Et}$, +H), 117 (16), 104 (8), 97 (9), 91 (13), 83 (12), 77 (16), 69 (21), 57 (25).

Cross condensation of acetylacetone and ethyl cyanoacetate in presence of K_2CO_3 : The same procedure was followed as before. After usual work-up the residue (3.5 g) was subjected to column chromatography.

4,6-Dimethyl-Z-2-(cyanoethoxycarbonyl)-1,2-dihydropyridine (3) : The light yellow gummy solid obtained from the light petrol ethyl acetate (9 : 1) eluate fractions was rechromatographed and purified by several crystallizations from CHCl_3 -light petrol to afford 4,6-dimethyl-Z-2-(cyanoethoxycarbonyl)-1,2-dihydropyridine (**3**) as light yellow needles (1.62 g, 30%), m.p. 190°.

Other fractions did not show any well-defined spot on tlc and did not yield any pure compound.

Cross condensation reaction of ethyl acetoacetate and ethyl cyanoacetate : After usual work-up, the residue (~5.5 g) was subjected to column chromatography.

3-Cyano-4-hydroxy-6-methyl-Z-2-(cyanoethoxycarbonyl)-2H-pyran (4) : The deep yellow gummy solid obtained from the later light petrol-ethyl acetate (1 : 4) eluate fractions showing a single spot on tlc gave 3-cyano-4-hydroxy-6-methyl-Z-2-(cyanoethoxycarbonyl)-2H-pyran (**4**) crystallizing from CHCl_3 -ethyl acetate as deep yellow needles (3.5 g, 70%), m.p. 269°; ν_{max} 3490–3500 (OH), 2979, 2190–2200 (CN), 1695 (conjugated ester C=O), 1660, 1550, 1520, 1430 (aromatic C=C), 1300, 1240, 1202, 1150, 1062, 962, 845, 765, 750 cm^{-1} ; δ_{H} (D_2O) 6.34 (1H, bs, H-5), 1.96 (3H, s, CH_3), 3.94 (2H, q, $\text{COOCH}_2\text{CH}_3$), 1.11 (3H, t, $\text{COOCH}_2\text{-CH}_3$); δ_{C} (DMSO) 170.23 ($\text{COOCH}_2\text{CH}_3$), 165.25 (C-2), 76.86 (C-3), 159.32 (C-4), 97.12 (C-5), 160.37 (C-6), 117.77 ($\text{CNCOOCH}_2\text{CH}_3$), 118.99 (CN at C-3), 65.63 ($\text{CNCCO}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_3$), 58.59 ($\text{COOCH}_2\text{CH}_3$), 20.73 (CH_3), 14.46 ($\text{COOCH}_2\text{CH}_3$); *m/z* (% rel. int.) : 246 (M^+ , 13), 174 (65), 146 (32), 134 (29), 120 (14), 119 (13), 91 (22), 78 (37), 69 (51), 45 (76), 41 (100).

Cross condensation of 2,4-dimethyl-6-hydroxyacetophenone and ethyl cyanoacetate :

The reaction was performed following the general procedure of cross condensation reaction by taking 2,4-dimethyl-6-hydroxyacetophenone (0.82 g, 0.005 mol) and ethyl cyanoacetate (5 ml, 0.04 mol) in presence of K_2CO_3 (0.003 mol). After usual work-up the residue obtained (0.35 g) was subjected to column chromatography on a wet column.

3-Cyano-4,5,7-trimethylcoumarin (5) : The red gummy solid obtained from the later light petrol-ethyl acetate (7 : 3) eluate fractions showing a single spot on tlc, afforded 3-cyano-4,5,7-trimethylcoumarin (**5**), crystallizing from CHCl_3 -light petrol as red needles (0.016 g, 25%), m.p. 215°; ν_{max} 2200 (CN), 1730 br (coumarin C=O), 1610, 1580, 1530, 1480, 1430 (aromatic C=C), 1380, 1320, 1290, 1260, 1160, 1095, 970, 860, 760, 740 cm^{-1} ; δ_{H} 2.91 (3H, s, CH_3),

2.72 (3H, s, CH_3), 2.41 (3H, s, CH_3), 7.00 (1H, s, H-6), 7.03 (1H, s, H-8); δ_{C} 168.68 (CO), 102.0 (C-3), 155.0 (C-4), 145.95 (C-5), 131.01 (C-6), 138.2 (C-7), 116.60 (C-8), 114.12 (CN), 115.70 (C-4a), 156.63 (C-8a); *m/z* (% rel.int.) 213 (M^+ , 100), 185 (36), 170 (70), 154 (19), 140 (11), 128 (12), 115 (22), 102 (5), 91 (11), 77 (15).

4,5,7-Trimethyl-Z-2-(cyanoethoxycarbonyl)methylenebenzo[b]-2H-pyran (6) : The deep yellow solid obtained from the middle light petrol-ethyl acetate (19 : 1) eluate fractions showing its homogeneity on tlc, afforded 4,5,7-trimethyl-Z-2-(cyanoethoxycarbonyl)methylenebenzo[b]pyran (**6**), crystallizing from CHCl_3 -light petrol as yellow flakes (0.027 g, 30%), m.p. 205°; ν_{max} 2980 (aromatic), 2200 (CN), 1700 (ester C=O), 1625, 1595, 1545, 1480, 1455, 1384, 1370, 1265, 1230, 1165, 1140, 1100, 1030, 1000, 970, 870, 855 cm^{-1} ; δ_{H} 7.74 (1H, s, H-3), 6.83 (1H, s, H-6), 6.92 (1H, s, H-8), 2.53 (6H, s, $2\times\text{CH}_3$), 2.54 (3H, s, CH_3), 4.19 (2H, q, $\text{O-CH}_2\text{CH}_3$), 1.29 (3H, t, $\text{OCH}_2\text{-CH}_3$); δ_{C} 164.32 (C-2), 116.39 (C-3), 149.19 (C-4), 143.0 (C-5), 130.61 (C-6), 136.69 (C-7), 115.93 (C-8), 117.9 (C-4a), 153.28 (C-8a), 76.08 ($\text{CCO}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_3$), 168.39 ($\text{COOCH}_2\text{CH}_3$), 60.55 ($\text{COOCH}_2\text{CH}_3$), 14.25 ($\text{COOCH}_2\text{CH}_3$), 117.9 (CN), 25.42 (CH_3), 23.97 (CH_3), 21.07 (CH_3); *m/z* (% rel.int.) 283 (M^+ , 55), 255 (15), 238 (58), 211 (100), 194 (8), 186 (30), 166 (18), 153 (9), 140 (12), 128 (9), 115 (15), 103 (4), 91 (9), 77 (10), 63 (10), 51 (8).

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Dr. M. Ogura (Tokyo) for his timely help in providing the mass spectra, and to Mr. A. Acharya, Mr. P. Ghosh and Mr. J. Ghosh of our Department for the ^1H , ^{13}C and IR spectral measurements. Financial assistance of the Department of Science and Technology, New Delhi, by way of a Research Project and of the University Grants Commission, New Delhi, in the form of Senior Research Fellowships to two of the authors (K.M. and S.M.) are gratefully acknowledged.

References

1. J. L. Simonsen and M. Nayak, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1915, 793.
2. S. K. Talapatra, P. Pal, K. Biswas, A. Shaw, R. Chakrabarti and B. Talapatra, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1998, 75, 590.
3. A. Hadi, M. Martin, C. Seoane and J. L. Soto, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans. 1*, 1993, 1045.
4. J. B. Strothers, "Carbon-1 NMR Spectroscopy", Academic, New York, 1972.
5. Y. D. Wu, K. N. Houk and B. M. Trost, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1987, 109, 5560.

6. M. Chérest, H. Felkin and N. Prudent, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1968, 2199.
7. F. A. Carey and M. E. Kuehne, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1982, 47, 3811.
8. E. L. Eliel and S. H. Wilen, "Stereochemistry of Organic Compounds", Wiley, New York, 1984, p 122; D. Nasipuri, "Stereochemistry of Organic Compounds", New Age International (P)